

Heat as a Proxy Tracer for Gas Exchange Measurements in the Field: Principles and Technical Realization

H. Haußecker^{1,3}, *S. Reinelt*², and *B. Jähne*^{1,3}

¹Scripps Institution of Oceanography, Physical Oceanography Res. Div.
La Jolla, CA 92093-0230, USA, email: bjaehne@ucsd.edu

²Institute for Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg
Im Neuenheimer Feld 366, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany

³Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing, University of Heidelberg
Im Neuenheimer Feld 368, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany
email: horst.haussecker@iwr.uni-heidelberg.de

Abstract

An infrared technique to investigate the transfer processes across the aqueous mass boundary layer is presented. This controlled flux technique (CFT) uses heat as a proxy tracer for gases to allow for fast and local measurements of the gas transfer rate. Three different ways of gas transfer velocity measurements are investigated. The first one, the steady state method is a straightforward way to probe the basic unknowns needed to directly compute the gas transfer velocity k . The other two proposed techniques are model based but also yield a deeper insight into the mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange. The decay method works only in a lab environment while the spatio-temporal temperature fluctuation method is well suited for both lab and ocean measurements. The mathematical foundations of the underlying models are introduced together with their practical application.

1 Introduction

The transfer rate k for any species (heat, gases or momentum) in water is directly related to the tracer flux across the interface and the resulting concentration difference across the aqueous boundary layer by

$$k = \frac{j}{\Delta c}, \quad (1)$$

with j = flux density of the observed species and Δc = concentration difference across the boundary layer. For heat Δc has to be replaced by the temperature difference ΔT , with $\Delta c = \rho C_p \Delta T$. The relation between k and the characteristic time constant t_* of the transport process is given by

$$t_* = \frac{D}{k^2}, \quad (2)$$

independently of the underlying model. Heat – like a dissolved gas tracer – is a scalar. Thus convective transport of both is the same, only the molecular transport differs. The ratio between gas and heat exchange rates, k_g/k_h , can be expressed as [Jähne *et al.*, 1989]

$$\frac{k_g}{k_h} = \left(\frac{D_g}{D_h}\right)^n = \left(\frac{Sc_g}{Sc_h}\right)^{-n}, \quad (3)$$

where the (dimensionless) *Schmidt number* Sc is defined as the ratio of kinematic viscosity ν to the diffusion coefficient D , $Sc = \nu/D$. The exponent ranges between 1/2 and 2/3 depending on the friction velocity and the mean square slope of the waves. Using this relation, the transfer velocity of any gas can be estimated if the transfer velocity of heat is known. Only the diffusion coefficients of the tracer and the Schmidt number exponent n have to be known accurately enough. Using a ± 0.02 uncertainty for n and a relative error for the diffusion coefficient D of 5%, the maximum absolute error of the gas exchange rate calculated from the heat transfer is about 12%.

In the following section, three different methods are introduced to measure the transfer velocity for heat exchange k_{heat} . These are:

- *steady state method*
- *decay method*
- *spatio-temporal temperature fluctuation method.*

2 Techniques, Models and Simulation

2.1 Steady State Method

If a known *heat flux* density of artificial *infrared radiation* is used to heat up the water surface, the transfer rate for heat in water can directly be determined from the resulting temperature response at the surface by (1). If the heat flux density j is well known k is inversely proportional to the temperature difference ΔT in the state of equilibrium. With the heat source turned on and off periodically ΔT can be measured directly out of the temperature increase right at the surface. The temperature response itself can very easily be measured with an infrared camera that observes the temperature distribution at the water surface.

2.2 Decay Method

The second method is to determine the time constant t_* of gas transfer out of the systems' response to a short temperature increase. This time the radiation is focused on a small spot that is heated up for a short time. If this heat spot can be tracked with an imaging thermography system the temporal decay of the temperature right at the surface yields t_* and therefore k since D is well known (2). Analytical and numerical solutions for the temporal

decay of a heat blob for different boundary layer models have already been developed by *Reinelt* [1994].

He solved the differential equations for the two boundary models *diffusion model* and *surface renewal model* [*Dankwerts*, 1951] for the one-dimensional case:

$$\frac{\partial C_d(z, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C_d(z, t)}{\partial z^2} \quad \text{and} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_{sr}(z, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C_{sr}(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - \lambda C_{sr}(z, t), \quad (5)$$

with the statistical renewal rate λ and a constant diffusion coefficient D . The time constant of the renewal effect $\tau = 1/\lambda$ describes the mean life span of a water surface element in between two surface renewal effects. Let $f(z, t)$ be a solution of (4) and $g(z, t)$ a solution of (5). Then f and g automatically are related by $g(z, t) = f(z, t)e^{-\lambda t}$.

Thus for a given initial concentration distribution within the boundary layer $C(z, 0)$ the temporal solution $C(z, t)$ of (4) and 5 is given by

$$C_d(z, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi Dt}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} C(\xi, 0) e^{-\frac{(z-\xi)^2}{4Dt}} d\xi \quad \text{and} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{sr}(z, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi Dt}} e^{-\lambda t} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} C(\xi, 0) e^{-\frac{(z-\xi)^2}{4Dt}} d\xi, \quad (7)$$

as a superposition of the elementary solutions of (4) and (5).

The instrumental setup consisted of a CO₂ infrared laser at a wavelength of 10.6 μm as heat source. The beam was focused and scanned in cross-wind direction producing a uniform flux distribution in this direction over a length of 13 cm and a laser profile shaped distribution in wind direction. Thus the whole decay process can be considered to be one-dimensional with the wind direction defining the time axis. The spatial distribution of the laser flux density is determined within the temperature images by means of digital mage processing techniques and subsequently used as spatially inhomogeneous boundary conditions in the simulation. The resulting temperature depth profile after the surface element has left the irradiated area can best be approximated by the Gaussian distribution

$$C(z, 0) = C_o e^{-\frac{z^2}{h^2}}, \quad -\infty < z < 0, \quad (8)$$

with the penetration depth $h/2$. This is used as the initial temperature distribution within the boundary layer. Combining (6), (7) and (8) yields

$$C_d(z, t) = C_o \frac{h}{\sqrt{h^2 + 4Dt}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{h^2 + 4Dt}} \quad \text{and} \quad (9)$$

$$C_{sr}(z, t) = C_o \frac{h}{\sqrt{h^2 + 4Dt}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{h^2 + 4Dt} - \lambda t}, \quad (10)$$

Figure 1: Decay curves of the water surface temperature after leaving the irradiated area. Left: Measurements with surface film. Data fitted with the two possible model-based decay functions for a wind speed of 8.8 m/s. Right: Decay curves for different wind speeds, measured without surface films.

for the two different boundary layer models. The infrared camera is sensitive in the 3–5 μm wavelength region. The corresponding penetration depth is about 20 μm , less than 5% of the typical heat boundary layer depth. Thus the temperature observed by the camera can be considered to be the surface temperature $T(0, t)$. The measured spatio-temporal temperature distribution therefore consist of the solutions (9) or (10) at $z = 0$:

$$C_d(0, t) = C_o \frac{h}{\sqrt{h^2 + 4Dt}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{sr}(0, t) = C_o \frac{h}{\sqrt{h^2 + 4Dt}} e^{-\lambda t}. \tag{11}$$

One of them should reflect the real averaged temperature development observed by the camera.

The unknown parameters of (11) are C_o , h and λ . C_o is the temperature of the decay curve at any time chosen as a starting point. Fitting the data to the decay curve yields the two remaining parameters. It shows that the surface renewal solution always provides better fits to the data than the diffusion model curve (Figure 1). Therefore the surface renewal decay curve is used for all further data evaluation with the *decay method*. The heat transfer rate k_{heat} can directly be computed out of (2) with $t_* = \lambda^{-1}$. Figure 2 shows some results of heat transfer rates computed with the decay method out of data from different wind-wave facilities. They are in good agreement with previously measured mass transfer values.

Figure 2: Gas transfer rates computed with the decay method for measurements at different wind wave facilities (Triangles: Linear Tank of Delft Hydraulics, The Netherlands. Rest: Circular Heidelberg facility). Open squares and triangles: decay method. Rest: previous mass transfer measurements.

2.3 Spatio-Temporal Temperature Fluctuation Method

The fact that the heat distribution at the water surface can directly be observed with a high spatial and temporal resolution offers another possibility to measure k and to get information about the transport mechanisms themselves. It was a main discovery during the first measurements with a new AMBER Radiance 1 infrared camera, that the typical natural heat fluxes across the water surface due to *radiative cooling* and *evaporation* are sufficiently large to cause significant temperature variations at the water surface. Since these variations are due to vertical mixing processes the heat patterns consist of both, the surface temperature and upwelling bulk water. With this discovery it is possible to estimate the temperature difference across the heat boundary layer out of the spatial temperature distribution. In this way the transport mechanisms become visible without any further application of external radiation. Nevertheless a model is needed to interpret the image content appropriately.

Previous measurements with the *decay method* showed that the surface renewal model is in best correspondence with the measured data. Therefore we use this model for a numerical simulation of the anticipated temporal temperature distribution. The concept of the surface renewal theory is that the fluid on the surface is periodically renewed by bulk fluid with a statistical renewal rate λ . The time constant of the renewal process τ is given by $\tau = 1/\lambda$. It has the physical meaning of the mean live span of a surface water patch. Given a constant tracer flux density j across the interface, the difference between water surface temperature and bulk temperature, $\Delta T(t)$ is directly proportional to the square root of the elapsed time since the last

Figure 3: Qualitative sketch of temporal surface temperature evolution for the surface renewal model with randomly distributed renewal effects.

renewal effect. Combining equations (1) and (2) yields

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{j_{heat}}{\rho C_p \sqrt{D}} \sqrt{t} = \alpha \sqrt{t}. \quad (12)$$

For a typical heat flux density of $j = 150 \text{ W/m}^2$, $\alpha = 0.0959$. Numerical simulations of the temperature evolution for the same heat flux density as boundary condition yield $\alpha = 0.1088$. Without surface renewal effects the surface temperature would continuously decrease according to (12). Introducing a statistical renewal, the temperature randomly drops back to the initial bulk water temperature T_o . Figure 3 shows a qualitative sketch of the surface temperature increase with renewal drop offs for a heat flux heating up the water surface.

The probability $P(t, \lambda)$ that a surface element would have an age of t , for a certain renewal rate $\lambda = 1/\tau_o$, is given by [Dankwerts, 1951, Gulliver, 1991]

$$P(t, \tau_o) = \lambda e^{-\lambda t}. \quad (13)$$

With this distribution the expectation value $\langle \Delta T \rangle$ of the surface temperature can be computed. This should be the mean temperature visible in the infrared images (Figure 3). The mean value $\overline{\Delta T}(\tau)$ of a single temperature increase in between two surface renewal effects with the temporal distance τ is given by

$$\overline{\Delta T}(\tau) = \tau^{-1} \int_0^\tau dt \Delta T(t). \quad (14)$$

The expectation value for ΔT is computed as the expectation value for all mean values $\overline{\Delta T}$ for all possible τ with $p(\tau, \tau_o)$ given in (13):

$$\langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o} = \int_0^\infty d\tau \overline{\Delta T}(\tau) p(\tau, \tau_o) \quad (15)$$

$$= \int_0^\infty d\tau \left[\tau^{-1} \int_0^\tau dt \Delta T(t) \right] p(\tau, \tau_o). \quad (16)$$

For a periodical renewal effect, i.e. $p(t, \tau_o) = \delta(t - \tau_o)$, (15) reduces to $\langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o} = \overline{\Delta T}(\tau_o)$. The variance σ^2 of the temperature distribution is given by

$$\sigma_{\tau_o}^2 = \int_0^\infty d\tau \left[\tau^{-1} \int_0^\tau dt (\Delta T(t) - \langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o})^2 \right] p(\tau, \tau_o). \quad (17)$$

For the temperature difference in (12) equations (15) and (17) reduce to

$$\langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o} = \frac{2\alpha}{3\tau_o} \int_0^\infty d\tau \sqrt{\tau} e^{-\frac{\tau}{\tau_o}} \quad \text{and} \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_{\tau_o}^2 = \frac{\alpha^2}{2\tau_o} \left[\int_0^\infty d\tau \tau e^{-\frac{\tau}{\tau_o}} \right] - \langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o}^2, \quad \text{respectively.} \quad (19)$$

A numerical evaluation of equations (18) and (19) for different τ_o shows that the ratio γ between the expectation value of the temperature difference $\langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o}$ and the standard deviation of the temperature distribution σ_{τ_o} is independent from τ_o :

$$\gamma = \frac{\langle \Delta T \rangle_{\tau_o}}{\sigma_{\tau_o}} = 0.657393 \approx \frac{2}{3} \quad \forall \tau_o. \quad (20)$$

This result opens up a very simple opportunity to estimate the temperature difference across the interface. Instead of directly measuring the difference between the mean surface temperature and some estimated bulk temperature it is sufficient to compute the standard deviation σ of the surface temperature distribution. The mean temperature difference across the interface is given by (20) and thus

$$k_{heat} = \gamma \frac{j}{\rho C_p \sigma}. \quad (21)$$

These results are used to estimate the heat transfer rate out of the image temperature distribution. Since the surface renewal is a statistical effect it should be equally distributed in space and time. Therefore every image is supposed to contain a variety of surface temperature states in between recent renewal and long periods of undisturbed cooling. The significance of this statistical assumption increases if the camera moves over the water surface and thus shows a variety of heat patterns with time.

A further test for the validity of the underlying model can be undertaken comparing the temperature distribution within the infrared images with the theoretical distribution for the modelled process. Given the temporal evolution of the surface temperature (12) the relative frequency $h(\Delta T, \tau)$ of ΔT for a certain τ computes as

$$h(\Delta T, \tau) = \frac{2}{\alpha^2} \frac{\Delta T}{\tau}. \quad (22)$$

Figure 4: Measured temperature distribution within one single image (grey area plot) together with the theoretical distribution (black squares). The corresponding noise variance is indicated by the solid black curve. The image was acquired during night time with clear sky at a wind speed of 5 m/s east of Catalina island, California.

The total frequency $h(\Delta T, \tau_o)$ of a certain τ_o is given by

$$h(\Delta T, \tau_o) = \frac{2}{\alpha^2} \Delta T \int_{\Delta T^2/\alpha^2}^{\infty} d\tau \frac{p(\tau, \tau_o)}{\tau}. \quad (23)$$

Figure 4 shows both the theoretical and the measured frequency distribution of one single image. Both are in good correspondance. This clearly supports the assumed boundary layer model. Also the temperature distribution within one single image seems to be representative for the process and thus allows to compute k out of (21) for each image, i. e., 60 times per second!

Haußecker et al. [1995] have successfully used this technique in the field during the MBL/COOP West Coast experiment in April/May 1995 aboard R/V New Horizon. Preliminary results are discussed in this paper together with the experimental setup of the sea-going instrument.

3 Conclusions

The various possibilities proposed in this article make the CFT a very versatile instrument to probe the gas transfer velocity and to get an insight into the mechanisms governing gas exchange. With three different techniques the results can mostly be verified against each other. The setup used within the lab experiments and the field going instrument proved to work well. However, some more detailed simulations have to be done to model the physical properties of the camera and water surface (e. g., finite penetration depth of both camera sensitive radiation and radiative cooling). A very promising result is the fact, that even a rough model seems to reflect the main principles of air-sea gas exchange.

Acknowledgements

Financial support of this research by the Office of Naval Research (N00014-93-1-0515 and N00014-94-1-0050) and by the National Science Foundation (OCE 89 11224) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- Dankwerts, P. V., Significance of Liquid-Film Coefficients in Gas Adsorption, *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, Vol. 43(6), pp. 1460-1467, 1951
- Gulliver, J. S., Introduction to Air-Water Mass Transfer, *Air-Water Mass Transfer*, selected papers from the 2nd International Symposium on Gas Transfer at Water Surfaces, September 11-14, 1991, Minneapolis, Minnesota, S. C. Wilhelms and J. S. Gulliver, eds, pp. 244-256, ASCE, New York., 1991
- Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, In situ measurements of the air-sea gas transfer rate using heat as a proxy tracer, *Second International Conference on Air-Sea Interaction and Meteorology and on Oceanography of the Coastal Zone*, Lisbon, September 22-27, 1994, Lisbon, Portugal, 1994
- Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, In situ measurements of the air-sea gas transfer rate during the MBL/COOP West Coast Experiment, *this volume*.
- Jähne, B., P. Libner, R. Fischer, T. Billen, and E. J. Plate, Investigating the transfer processes across the free aqueous viscous boundary layer by the controlled flux method, *Tellus* (1989), *41B*, pp. 177-195, 1989
- Jähne, B., From mean fluxes to a detailed experimental investigation of the gas transfer process, *Air-Water Mass Transfer*, selected papers from the 2nd International Symposium on Gas Transfer at Water Surfaces, September 11-14, 1991, Minneapolis, Minnesota, S. C. Wilhelms and J. S. Gulliver, eds, pp. 244-256, ASCE, New York, 1991
- Reinelt, S., Bestimmung der Transfergeschwindigkeit mittels CFT mit Wärme als Tracer, *Diploma thesis*, Institute for Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg, August 1994